

**CREEP BEHAVIOUR OF THE METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE
Al 2124 WITH SiC FIBRES**

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ABSTRACT

The creep deformation of the metal matrix composite Al 2124 with SiC fibres is studied at 300°C. The strain vs. time curves shows three stages, with a fairly long stage I, a well-developed stage II and an extremely short stage III. The creep rates vs. applied stress demonstrate improvements in creep strength, but less than predicted by (simple) models for aligned fibre composites. The stress sensitivity of the creep rate is larger for the composite than for the matrix alloy; this is interpreted to indicate possibly complex interactions between fibres and the precipitation process.

INTRODUCTION

Several metal matrix composite materials are based on existing high strength alloys, typically Al-alloys which derive their strength from precipitation hardening. Some commercially available metal matrix composites are made from such Al-alloys with added (short) fibres. In most cases increases in strength, both for short time and long time, are obtained; but it is not always clear and seldom evaluated in detail whether the added fibres achieve the strength contribution which should be expected (e.g.

from fibre mechanics modelling of the strength).

The models attempt to predict the (maximum) gain in creep strength of the composite materials for various fibre configurations, i.e. long fibres, short fibres, non-aligned fibres (off-axis loading) and random fibres. The models are based on simple concepts for the mechanics of loading and load distribution between fibres and matrix. Models for composites with short aligned fibres loaded along the fibre direction have been presented (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6); the case of long fibres has also been treated (5, 6), as well as non-aligned and random fibre orientations (6). The description of creep of general composite materials has been given in outline (7). The possible fracture or creep of the fibres themselves has been discussed (1, 3, 5, 7). In most cases the dependence of the creep rate on the applied stress has been evaluated, and especially the constant (steady state; stage II) creep rate has been considered, although also primary (stage I) creep has been treated (6). Recently, modelling of the final creep period (tertiary, stage III) before failure has been attempted (8).

Most of these models have been tested on composite materials of an experimental (or model) nature, e.g. copper reinforced with tungsten wires, and on directionally solidified eutectic alloy systems. In general good agreement has been found for these model materials.

The present study attempts to evaluate the creep strengthening effect of fibres for the commercially available composite of Al 2124 alloy with SiC fibres in the form of short whiskers. The matrix alloy is precipitation hardening, and fibre volume fractions are 15 and 25 vol%; the fibre orientation is not well defined because of the processing route used for the composite, but some alignment of the fibres exists.

The experiments comprise creep curves (strain versus time) under uniaxial loading at different stress levels; the steady-state, constant creep rate is evaluated and related to the applied stress, to study the models and their predictive capability for the short fibre metal matrix composite.

MATERIALS

The metal matrix composite has a matrix of Al 2124 alloy, which is a conventional aircraft alloy. The major alloying elements are Cu, Mg and Mn causing the alloy to be precipitation hardening.

The fibres are SiC whiskers of α -type, made from rice hulls (Silag operation, ARCO-firm), with the following characteristics:

Diameter	~0.6 μm
Length	10-80 μm
Density	3.3 g/cm^3
Whisker content	80-90 %.

The composite is fabricated by the powder metallurgy route: the matrix powder and the fibres are mixed, pressed, extruded, and rolled to plate, with the rolling direction at right angle to the extrusion direction. The plate is 6.5 mm thick and is given the heat treatment T6 to cause precipitation hardening.

The mixing step and the cross-rolling step are likely to produce a fibre orientation distribution which is not well defined, some alignment (from the extrusion step) is expected.

Three materials are used in the study:

- Al 2124 alloy (pure matrix)
- Al 2124 + 15 vol% SiC
- Al 2124 + 25 vol% SiC.

From the as-fabricated plates, specimens were machined for creep testing. Two series of specimens were tested, series 1 with the specimen axis parallel to the extrusion direction, and series 2 with the specimen axis at right angle to the extrusion direction.

CREEP TESTING

The creep experiments were carried out as constant load testing, which is very nearly identical to constant stress conditions because the creep strain is of the order of only a few per cent. The creep specimens were cylindrical with a diameter of 4.5 mm and a gauge length of approximately 46 mm. The temperature was 300°C and specimens were at temperature for about one hour before start of the creep test. The creep curves, i.e. strain versus time, were recorded.

Figure 1a. Schematic creep curve.

Figure 1b. Creep curve for Al 2124 with 15% SiC fibres, temperature 300°C, stress 48 MPa.

RESULTS

The results and related discussion comprise a qualitative evaluation of the creep curves and a more quantitative evaluation of the relation between creep rate and applied stress.

The creep curves all have the form sketched in Fig. 1; the curves can be characterised by three stages, stage I with a decreasing creep rate, stage II with a constant creep rate, and stage III with an (often rapidly)

increasing creep rate, followed by final, local failure.

The qualitative evaluation of the creep curves for the two composite materials is that stage I often comprises a large part of the total creep time. Under such conditions stage II is often short, and somewhat difficult to define. At relatively low stresses the stage I seems to be completed, and stage II is established rather well over relatively long durations of creep. In all cases stage III is rather brief and has a rapidly increasing creep rate, resulting in relatively large creep strains under stage III conditions.

A qualitative inspection of the creep curves gives the following durations of the creep stages, expressed in fractions of the total creep time:

TABLE 1

Material	Fraction of total creep time		
Al 2124.	Low stress	stage I	≤ 0.1
		stage II	≥ 0.8
		stage III	$\approx 0.1-0.2$
	High stress	stage I	≤ 0.1
		stage II	$\sim 0.5-0.6$
		stage III	$\sim 0.3-0.4$
Al 2124 + 15% SiC.	Low stress	stage I	≤ 0.3
		stage II	≥ 0.7
		stage III	short
	High stress	difficult to define	
Al 2124 + 25% SiC.		stage I	≤ 0.5
		stage II	≥ 0.5
		stage III	very short

The creep rate in stage II is estimated from the creep curves. This estimate is sometimes difficult because of the transition from stage I to II described above. It is, however, of interest to find a (possible) stage II creep rate in order to study the stress dependence of the creep rate.

The results are presented in Figs. 2 and 3. These plots are the log of creep rate versus the stress; this presentation essentially refers to the exponential creep law (rather than the power creep law for metals). The

Figure 2. Creep rates in stage II for Al 2124 + SiC fibres, series 1 with loading along the extrusion direction.

Figure 3. Creep rates in stage II for Al 2124 + SiC fibres, series 2 with loading across the extrusion direction.

reasons for this choice of plot are partly the physical arguments of relatively high in-situ creep rates of the matrix, partly the convenience of the linear scale for the creep stress which aids in the evaluation of stress contributions to creep strength. The details of these arguments are pres-

ented earlier in (4) which discusses creep laws for metals, and (5) where details of the models and methods of analysis are given.

For both series of experiments the results show an improvement in creep strength with the pure alloy creeping at about 40 MPa, while the composites creep at about 50 and 70 MPa, respectively, for 15 and 25 vol% of SiC fibres. The series 1 data show slightly higher creep strengths for the composites, probably indicating some fibre alignment parallel to the extrusion direction. For both series the stress sensitivity of the composite creep rates is very high, and larger than that of the pure alloy.

DISCUSSION

The creep curves (Table 1 and Fig. 1) demonstrate the relative significance of the deformation mechanisms which are active in fibre reinforced metals (and the pure matrix). The extent of stage I increases with volume fraction of fibres, roughly proportionally. This tendency can be understood in terms of the load (re-)distribution between fibres and matrix during creep. Typically, the matrix is rather creep compliant, while the fibres are rather creep resistant, if not fully rigid (i.e. non-creeping).

For a constant, applied stress on a fibrous composite an initial stress distribution is established between matrix and fibres, typically the matrix creeps while the fibres deform elastically. After further creep time, this causes a redistribution of stress, so that the matrix stress decreases and the fibre stress increases, thus causing the creep rate to decrease, this situation constitutes stage I.

This type of creep deformation is visco-elastic; if at same time other creep producing mechanisms are activated, the (total) creep deformation will increase over and above the level governed by the visco-elastic process. Such mechanisms could be local plastic deformation around fibre ends, or failure at or near fibre ends, where the incompatible deformation between matrix and fibres is most pronounced. Attempts to model such mechanisms have been made (8). The contribution from these additional deformation processes cannot be assessed independently; on the other hand, the existence of a marked and extended stage II (see Table 1) indicates that they are active and cause the (total) recorded creep rate to be constant, i.e. stage II conditions. The extent of stage II decreases slightly with volume fraction of fibres, especially at 25 vol%.

The final period of creep, stage III, is relatively extended for the

pure matrix, while it is extremely short for the composites. In the pure matrix the mechanisms (e.g. cavity formation) leading to higher creep rates are active uniformly over the specimen volume; in the composites the more highly stressed regions near fibre ends are likely to be the places of initiation and accumulation of creep damage. This would imply a much shorter time for the composites to reach a state of catastrophic amount of damage and thus final failure. An estimate of the creep rates in stage III (which is experimentally difficult) indicates that these are larger than the stage II creep rates by 3 to 5 orders of magnitude. This is comparable to the values obtained in the modelling (8) of stage III with debonded fibre/matrix interface.

The data for creep rates versus stress, Figs. 2 and 3, show clear improvements in the creep strength of the composites over that of the matrix alloy, although the improvement is not in quantitative agreement with the simple model for aligned short fibre composites (5).

The expected position of the composite curves in the creep diagram would be further to the right (larger stresses), and the slope of the composite curve is predicted to be lower than that of the matrix curve. On this basis the fibres in the composites do not contribute their full effect to the creep strength. A similar picture emerged (5) for the creep data on Al 6061 with 14 vol% SiC fibres reported by Nieh (9).

These deviations from the (simple) model in both the 2124 and 6061 alloy composites may indicate a possibly complex interaction between the microstructural parameters: fibres, precipitates and dislocations.

In both types of composites the fibre orientation is not perfectly aligned. The 2124 composites probably have nearly random orientations as indicated by the close numerical similarity between the creep data for the specimens cut along and across the extrusion direction. The 6061 composites have relatively well aligned fibres, according to (9). In both cases the deviation from perfect alignment will cause a reduction in the mean stress in the composite and thus increase the slope of the composite data in the creep diagrams (Fig. 2 and 3); for details see (5). However, the slope of the composite data should always be lower than that of the matrix (reference) material. Thus, the non-perfect fibre alignment cannot fully explain the data.

The precipitation process and the dislocation structure of the pure alloy govern the position of the matrix data in the creep diagram. It is possible that the fibres interact with or disturb the precipitation process

Figure 4. Creep rates in stage II for Al, Al 2124-composites and Al 6061-composites (9).

in the composites in a negative sense so that the in-situ matrix is different from the pure alloy matrix, and especially has a lower in-situ strength (as referred to creep).

Although the details of such an interaction are not clear, the creep data can be interpreted to show such negative interactions. This becomes perhaps more likely by comparing the matrix alloy (and the two composites) with the pure Al data (4) as plotted in Fig. 4. It is seen that the pure alloy on its own shows a rather large strengthening effect, while the additional effect of the fibres is relatively small. It seems necessary to further investigate such possible interactions to obtain a more efficient use of the fibres under creep conditions. With respect to the engineering

use of these composites Fig. 4 presents all the data (as best straight lines). The pure Al 2124 alloy data are reasonably consistent with the literature (Metals Handbook). The fibre reinforcement of the Al 2124 alloy is somewhat less efficient than the reinforcement of the 6061 alloy. As practical values for engineering use the Al 6061 with ~14 vol% SiC fibres has creep strengths very similar to those of the Al 2124 alloy with ~25 vol% SiC fibres. The evaluation of the mechanisms of fibre reinforcement under creep conditions seems complex, and simpler composites may be one way to sort out these interacting mechanisms; such an attempt has been made in a study of the internal stress in pure Al with 5 vol% SiC fibres (10).

CONCLUSIONS

Metal matrix composites of Al 2124 alloy with 15 and 25 vol% SiC fibres have been studied in creep.

The creep curves (strain versus time) show three stages; stage I (visco-elastic deformation) lasts longer for composites with higher SiC-fibre content; stage II is reasonably well defined (additional, local deformation processes); stage III is extremely short.

The creep rates versus applied stress show improvements in creep strength for the composites over the pure alloy, but the strengthening is significantly smaller than predicted by (simple) models for aligned short fibre composites.

The stress sensitivity of the creep rate is larger for the composites than for the matrix; this is interpreted as an indication of (possibly complex) interactions between the fibres and the precipitation process in the alloy matrix.

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